

CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS OF CARDIORESPIRATORY AND NEUROLOGICAL DISORDERS IN NEWBORN CHILDREN BORN TO MOTHERS WHO EXPERIENCED COVID-19 DURING PREGNANCY

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Abstract. *Objective of the study is to investigate the nature of clinical manifestations of cardiorespiratory and neurological disorders in preterm newborns born to mothers who experienced COVID-19 during pregnancy. A total of 70 preterm infants were examined. The first main group consisted of 40 infants born to mothers who experienced COVID-19 of varying severity during pregnancy, while the second group included 30 preterm infants whose mothers did not have COVID-19. Clinical-laboratory, instrumental, and statistical methods of research were conducted. A comparative assessment of clinical manifestations of respiratory, cardiovascular, and neurological disorders showed that in infants born to mothers who experienced severe COVID-19 during pregnancy, these conditions occurred more frequently than in the comparison group. The highest frequency of complications such as respiratory failure, cerebral edema, DIC syndrome, and NEC was noted in the group of infants born to mothers who had severe COVID-19.*

Keywords: *COVID-19, coronavirus infection, newborn, preterm infants.*

In recent years, the coronavirus infection COVID-19 has become a major medical issue worldwide. Its consequences have affected the work of doctors across all specialties, including neonatologists [1,3,9,10].

In the absence of differences in the frequency of pathological conditions in newborns depending on the timing of maternal COVID-19 manifestation, its severity is higher in newborns whose mothers experienced COVID-19 in the first or third trimesters of pregnancy, as confirmed by a higher incidence of conditions such as intrauterine infection (42.1%), perinatal damage to the central nervous system (36%), intrauterine growth restriction and malnutrition (12%), respiratory failure (20%), and congenital malformations (15.8%), for which a significant number of children require transfer to specialized neonatal units for treatment [3,7,11].

According to a systematic review of studies (100,000 subjects), vertical transmission of the virus to the fetus was documented in 5.4% of cases (5,400 cases). Additionally, in the group of pregnant women with SARS-CoV-2, the percentage of preterm infants was significantly higher (up to 25%) and the incidence of low birth weight infants (fetal growth restriction syndrome up to 25%); fetal distress occurred in 26.5–30.0%, newborn asphyxia - in 1.4%, and hospitalization of newborns in the intensive care unit was required in 43% of cases, with perinatal mortality ranging from 0.35% to 2.2% [2,4,12].

Russian researchers Kuneshko N.F. et al. found an inverse relationship between the weight of infants born to women who had experienced coronavirus infection and the severity of the disease (the greater the severity of the disease, the lower the birth weight of the infants). Infants born to

women who had COVID-19 more frequently received lower scores on the Apgar scale [5].

In the study by J. Li et al., biochemical analysis of umbilical cord blood at birth revealed a significant increase in myocardial enzymes, indicating severe myocardial damage in the fetus [6]. Various clinical manifestations have also been reported in observational series and case descriptions, ranging from thrombosis to atrioventricular conduction disturbances, as well illustrated by Sankaran et al. and Pawar et al. [8,10].

D.U. De Rose et al. noted patterns in the clinical manifestations of infected newborns. Initial symptoms may include fever, cough, or diarrhea. Although vertical transmission of COVID-19 has not yet been confirmed, perinatal infection can lead to premature birth, respiratory distress, thrombocytopenia, accompanied by liver dysfunction, and even death. For example, respiratory distress syndrome with late onset has been described in several infants 1-3 weeks after birth and/or discharge from the hospital [1,2].

Airway lesions range from mild respiratory infection to pneumonia complicated by severe acute respiratory distress syndrome, multiple organ failure, and death [5,10]. In very rare cases, newborns exhibit the development of multisystem inflammatory syndrome associated with a previous COVID-19 infection [7,13].

All children suspected of being infected with SARS-CoV-2 should be under medical supervision, regardless of the presence of clinical symptoms [5,7].

Objective of the study. To investigate the nature of clinical manifestations of cardiorespiratory and neurological disorders in premature newborns born to mothers who had COVID-19 during pregnancy.

Materials and methods. Our studies were conducted at the City Children's Hospital No. 5 and the City Perinatal Center. A total of 70 premature newborns were examined, divided into two groups. The main 1st group consisted of 40 premature newborns born to mothers who had COVID-19 of varying severity during pregnancy, while the 2nd comparison group comprised 30 premature newborns whose mothers did not have COVID-19 and were in the premature care unit.

The first group was further divided into two subgroups: subgroup 1a consisted of children born to mothers who had a mild course of COVID-19 in the form of ARVI (n=21), while subgroup 1b included newborns whose mothers had a severe course of COVID-19 in the form of coronavirus pneumonia (n=19).

Clinical-laboratory studies and neurosonography were conducted. Neurosonography was performed in real-time using transcranial ultrasound scanning of the brain according to standard sections in the frontal and sagittal planes on the SONOSCKOPESSI – 6000 device using a convex sensor of 5-7 MHz, a linear sensor of 5-10 MHz, and a sector sensor of 3-5 MHz.

Statistical processing of the obtained data was carried out using Microsoft Excel 2010 and Statistics 6.1 software packages, utilizing statistical functions, Student's t-test (t), and calculating the probability of error (P). Differences were considered statistically significant at $P < 0.05$.

Results and discussion. Our previous studies showed that in newborns whose mothers had COVID-19 during pregnancy, the most commonly encountered pathological conditions included anemia, hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy, intraventricular hemorrhages, congenital pneumonia, RDS, lung atelectasis, asphyxia, and intrauterine growth restriction. Notably, there was a significant predominance of the latter in children born to mothers who had a severe course of coronavirus infection [9].

Analysis of the structure of complications in these newborns showed that the highest frequency of complications such as respiratory failure, brain edema, DIC syndrome, and NEC was observed in the group of children born to mothers who had a severe course of COVID-19 (Table 1).

Thus, NEC in children in subgroup 1b occurred 2.2 times more often than in subgroup 1a and 3.2 times more often than in the comparison group. Brain edema and DIC syndrome developed in one child born to a mother who had a severe course of coronavirus infection during pregnancy.

Table 1.

Structure of complications of pathological conditions in premature children born to mothers who had COVID-19 of varying severity.

Complications	1st main group n-40		2nd comparison group n-30
	1a subgroup n-21	1b subgroup n-19	
Respiratory failure	76,1±9,3%	89,4±7,1%	73,3±8,1%
Cerebral edema	-	5,3±5,2%	-
DIC syndrome	-	5,3±5,2%	3,3±3,2%
NEC	4,7±4,6%	10,5±7,1%	3,3±3,2%

In the clinical observation of newborns, we conducted a comparative assessment of clinical disorders in the respiratory, cardiovascular, and nervous systems. The comparative assessment of respiratory disorders showed that in children born to mothers who had contracted a coronavirus infection, these disorders occurred more frequently than in children from the comparison group (Table 2).

Table 2.

Comparative characteristics of respiratory disorders in observed premature children

Clinical manifestations	1st main group n-40		2nd comparison group n-30
	1a subgroup n-21	1b subgroup n-19	
Dyspnea	76,1±9,3%	89,4±7,1%	73,3±8,1%
Apnea	19,0±8,6%	36,8±11,1%	6,7±4,5%
Cyanosis	85,7±7,7%	89,4±7,1%	80,0±7,3%
Acrocyanosis	47,6±10,9%	52,6±11,5%	26,7±8,1%
Flare of the alae nasi	47,6±10,9%	52,6±11,5%	23,3±7,8%
Retraction of intercostal spaces	76,1±9,3%	89,4±7,1%	73,3±8,1%
Weakened breathing	85,7±7,7%	89,4±7,1%	83,3±6,8%
Wheezing	28,5±9,8%	47,3±11,5%	20,0±7,3%

It is noteworthy that respiratory disorders in newborns born to mothers who experienced severe COVID-19 pneumonia were more common than in other children. Importantly, apnea in children born to mothers with severe coronavirus infection occurred 1.9 times more often than in

children of mothers with mild illness and 5.5 times more often than in children whose mothers did not have a coronavirus infection.

All signs of respiratory failure: shortness of breath, cyanosis, acrocyanosis, nasal flaring, intercostal retraction, as well as auscultatory data in children of subgroup 1b, born to mothers who experienced severe COVID-19, were significantly more common than in children of other groups. Next, we conducted an analysis of cardiovascular system disorders (Table 3). Our data showed that in premature newborns whose mothers contracted COVID-19 during pregnancy, cardiovascular disorders such as tachycardia, muffled heart sounds, pallor, marbling, and cold extremities were more frequent, especially in children of subgroup 1b.

Table 3.

Comparative characteristics of cardiovascular disorders in observed premature children

Clinical manifestations	1st main group n-40		2nd comparison group n-30
	1a subgroup n-21	1b subgroup n-19	
Tachycardia	71,4±9,8%	73,7±11,1%	50,0±9,1%
Muffled heart sounds	85,7±7,7%	89,5±7,1%	83,3±6,8%
Heart murmurs	76,1±9,3%	78,9±9,4%	76,7±7,7%
Paleness	85,7±7,7 (18)	89,5±7,1%	83,3±6,2%
Skin marbling	42,8±10,6 (9)	47,3±11,5%	40,0±9,1%
Cold extremities	38,1±10,6%	52,6±11,5%	26,7±8,1%
Edema	4,7±4,6%	10,5±7,1%	3,4±3,3%

Edema in children of group 1b occurred 2.2 times more often than in children of subgroup 1a and 3.1 times more often than in children of the comparison group. When studying the neurological status of the observed newborns, it was found that the excitation syndrome and convulsive syndrome in children whose mothers experienced severe COVID-19 occurred 2.2 times more often than in children whose mothers had a mild course of the disease (Table 4).

Additionally, the excitation syndrome in subgroup 1b occurred 3.1 times more often, and the convulsive syndrome occurred 2.1 times more often than in newborns from the comparison group. For all premature children, the neurological status was characterized by a predominance of the depression syndrome. However, the highest frequency of this syndrome was found in children whose mothers experienced severe COVID-19.

Table 4.

Comparative characteristics of clinical manifestations of the CNS in observed premature children

Clinical manifestations	1st main group n-40		2nd comparison group n-30
	1a subgroup n-21	1b subgroup n-19	
Excitation syndrome	9,5±5,4%	21,0±6,4%	6,7±3,4%
Convulsive syndrome	9,5±5,4%	21,0±6,4%	10,0±4,5%
Depression syndrome	81,0±6,7%	89,5±7,0%	76,7±6,7%

We also conducted an analysis of neurosonography in the observed children to identify pathological changes in the structures of the brain (Table 5).

The analysis showed that the most profound changes in the brain structures occur in premature newborns whose mothers had a severe coronavirus infection. Thus, the frequency of detecting immaturity of brain structures and hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy in subgroup 1b was higher than in children from other groups.

Table 5.

Pathological changes in the brain structure of observed premature children according to neurosonography data

Neurosonography indicators	1st main group n-40		2nd comparison group n-30
	1a subgroup n-21	1b subgroup n-19	
Immaturity of brain structures	80,9±8,6%	84,2±8,4%	70,0±8,4%
HIE	90,4±6,4%	94,7±4,9%	86,7±6,2%
IVH grade I	28,5±10,3%	21,1±6,4%	13,4±5,2%
IVH grade II	9,5±4,6%	5,2±4,1%	6,7±3,4%
IVH grade III	4,7±4,6%	26,4±8,1%*	10,0±4,5%
PVL	0	15,8±6,4%	6,7±3,4%
Small pseudocysts	4,7±4,6 %	10,5±5,0%	0
SEC	14,3±5,6%	15,8±3,4%	13,4±5,2%
Dilation of lateral ventricles	4,7±4,6%	15,8±3,4%*^	6,7±3,4%
Cerebral edema	-	5,2±4,1%	-

Note: * - significance of differences between subgroups 1a and 1b - $P < 0.001$; ^ - significance of differences between subgroup 1b and the comparison group - $P < 0.001$.

In children of group 1a, grade I respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) was most frequently identified at a rate of $28.5 \pm 10.3\%$, which was higher than in the other groups. However, grade III RDS was observed in more than a quarter of children in group 1b at a rate of $26.4 \pm 10.1\%$, which was significantly higher than in the children of group 1a and 2.6 times greater than in the comparison group. Periventricular leukomalacia (PVL) was observed in children of group 1b 2.4 times more often than in the comparison group. No cases of PVL were identified in group 1a. The frequency of certain epidemiological conditions (SEC) in the observed groups did not show significant differences. The dilation of the lateral ventricles was found to be significantly more common in children of group 1b than in those of group 1a and the comparison group. Additionally, one child in group 1b experienced brain swelling.

Thus, the comparative evaluation of clinical manifestations of respiratory, cardiovascular, and neurological disorders showed that in children born to mothers who had experienced severe COVID-19 during pregnancy, these disorders occurred more frequently than in children of the comparison group. The highest frequency of complications, such as respiratory failure, brain edema, disseminated intravascular coagulation syndrome (DIC), and necrotizing enterocolitis

(NEC), was noted in the group of children born to mothers who had a severe course of COVID-19.

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